

DISTRIBUTION MANAGEMENT OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT

Theoretical judgments lay the foundation of any research. In the present article, they outline the essence of the realization of agricultural products and allow to analyze the main ones features accompanying this process. Understanding the essence of the main types of agricultural production markets requires a characterization of each of them. In this sense, it is important to take into account the essence of a value chain in the agricultural sector, taking into account the peculiarities of agricultural production, the specificity of agricultural products, the entities through which production is realized, the demand for agricultural products, the organization of production and the realization of production and the management process itself in agricultural holdings.

KEYWORDS: distribution management, agricultural production, farm management

ABSTRAKT

Theoretische Urteile bilden die Grundlage jeder Forschung. Im vorliegenden Artikel wird das Wesen der Verwertung landwirtschaftlicher Erzeugnisse umrissen, und es werden die wichtigsten Merkmale dieses Prozesses analysiert. Um das Wesen der wichtigsten Arten von Märkten für landwirtschaftliche Erzeugnisse zu verstehen, muss jeder einzelne von ihnen charakterisiert werden. In diesem Sinne ist es wichtig, das Wesen einer Wertschöpfungskette im Agrarsektor zu berücksichtigen, unter Berücksichtigung der Besonderheiten der landwirtschaftlichen Produktion, der Spezifität der landwirtschaftlichen Produkte, der Einheiten, durch die die Produktion realisiert wird, der Nachfrage nach landwirtschaftlichen Produkten, der Organisation der Produktion und der Realisierung der Produktion und des Managementprozesses selbst in landwirtschaftlichen Betrieben.

STICHWORTE: Vertriebsmanagement, landwirtschaftliche Produktion, Betriebsführung

RÉSUMÉ

Les jugements théoriques constituent la base de toute recherche. Dans le présent article, ils exposent l'essence de la réalisation des produits agricoles et nous permettent d'analyser les principales caractéristiques qui accompagnent ce processus. Comprendre l'essence des principaux types de marchés de production agricole nécessite une caractérisation de chacun d'entre eux. Dans ce sens, il est important de prendre en compte l'essence d'une chaîne de valeur dans le secteur agricole, en tenant compte des particularités de la production agricole, de la spécificité des produits agricoles, des entités à travers lesquelles la production est réalisée, de la demande de produits agricoles, de l'organisation de la production et de la réalisation de la production et du processus de gestion lui-même dans les exploitations agricoles.

MOTS-CLÉS: gestion de la distribution, production agricole, gestion des exploitations agricoles

INTRODUCTION

The agricultural production system is a multifactorial open system, maintaining a stable dynamic equilibrium state through multiple connections of its constituent elements and interactions with other systems of the environment. It functions in conditions of uncertainty, predetermined by the economic and ecological factors of the individual microdistricts of the country [Kolaj, Borisov, Osmani, and Arabska, 2022]. These features predetermine the essence of the agricultural production system. It can be defined as a complex of interconnected and subordinated to varying degrees natural, biological, material, technical and other elements, combined (combined) in a complex dynamic unity, ensuring the production of agricultural products through the implementation of many interconnected processes [Borisov, & Popova, 2021]. The specificity of the agricultural production system is determined, on the one hand, by the features of its constituent elements and their combinations, and on the other by the interaction of the system itself with its surrounding environment [Kolaj, Borisov, Osmani, Arabska, Radev, 2021]. The immobility of the production base is the main prerequisite for the mobility of the means of labor, in contrast to other industries, where the subject of labor is more often the object of transportation [Kolaj, Borisov, Osmani and Arabska, 2022].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The restructuring of agricultural holdings is a relatively long process for most countries in the EU, but for Bulgaria the rates of change in the structure of agricultural holdings are one of the most significant [Radev, Borisov and Miladinovski, 2019]. According to data from the 2020 census, the number of agricultural holdings in Bulgaria meeting the threshold criteria specified in the Law on the Census of Agricultural Holdings in the Republic of Bulgaria in 2020 is 132,400 (graph 1), which is 64% less than the number reported during the 2010 census.

Figure 1. Number of agricultural holdings by year. Source: "Agrostatistics" MZHG – Bulgaria

In 2003, their absolute number was 665,548, and in 2010 – 370,222 in number, with the predominance of small and medium-sized farms. In 2020, they are only 132,633 farms. Of the total number of farms, 13,440 do not farm land. The submitted applications for support with direct area payments for 2020 are 57,822 in number, or this represents 44 percent of the total number of agricultural holdings in the country.

The total number of farms managing agricultural areas in 2020 is 119,193, which represents a drop of 67 percent compared to 2010. For the period under review, a significant increase in the used agricultural area (UAA) was registered. In 2003, the EPA was in the amount of 2,904,480 ha. After the country's accession to the EU, the interest in expanding the area of farms was significant and, accordingly, within three years, the agricultural area reached 3,616,965 ha (+25%). The average land size for holdings increased from 4 to 10 ha in 2010. This is a result of both an increase in arable land (+17%) and permanently grassed areas (+256%). In 2020, the average size of holdings reached 33 ha.

Figure 2. Average arable are of holdings with land (ha). Source: "Agrostatistics" MZHG – Bulgaria

In 2020, the agricultural area managed by agricultural holdings reached 3,959 thousand ha and increased by 9% compared to 2010 and by 34% compared to 2003. The average FZ of agricultural holdings with land increased to 33 ha, compared to 10 ha reported in 2010 (graph 2).

Economic activity in agriculture can be considered as a process in which a person interacts with nature to create material goods and at the same time interacts with other people in carrying out this process. The process is based on the creation of consumer value and its realization on the market. Therefore, agricultural economic activity includes two interrelated activities [Boevsky, 2020]. One is directly related to the attraction and use of resources to obtain a final product. And another activity refers to offering the product on the market and facilitating their consumption by considering the specifics of the market. These two activities are dynamic in nature and it is imperative that they be coordinated in order to achieve the objective of the business activity. These activities are subject to management by the agricultural producer to overcome the differences between the desired and the actual state of economic activity. Management is decision-making for the rational use of resources to achieve certain goals. Management is a process that is carried out under the influence of the results of already implemented decisions and their evaluation by the agricultural producer. In order to form his assessment, the owner (manager) must know well the structure and functioning of the farm (the object of management) and the purpose of its existence. This is a condition for clearly defining criteria for business development. Having an appropriate evaluation criterion allows, once development options have been developed,

In the process of making management decisions, the agricultural producer proceeds from the understanding that his economic activity is determined by consumer demand and, in the long term, should be considered as satisfying needs [Borisov, P., T. Radev (2020)]. Concentrating the producer's attention solely on the production process will limit his opportunities to participate in the supply of consumer value

in the marketing chain, but it is also a possible farm management strategy [Yovchevska, 2015]. Each agricultural holding has its own characteristics that have an impact on the organization and management of economic activity. Most often these are the type of product produced, the geographic location of the farm, the markets served, the technology used, the management philosophy and the market image of the farm.

The analysis of the production potential of the agricultural holding is an important prerequisite when developing a strategy for the realization of the production. In this context, a number of questions should be answered:

- what is the technological level of production;
- what resources does the farm have;
- what is the nature of the proceedings;
- can production be diversified;
- what production and economic results the agricultural holding achieves;
- what is the quality of the manufactured product and what criteria are used to determine the quality;
- what are the fixed and variable costs associated with each production and how are they managed over time.

The human factor is an integral part of any economic activity and is often of key importance for the successful functioning of the agricultural holding. In this sense, the qualities of the farmer and his philosophy on how to manage his farm are important in making management decisions. When assessing the potential of the agricultural producer, the purpose of his economic activity, his experience, his technological knowledge, knowledge of consumer behavior, his ability to motivate, his attitude towards economic entities in the marketing chain, interest in innovation are taken into account.

The market is the starting point for any economic activity and determines the parameters in which the agricultural holding functions. Each market has its own characteristics that must be known by the farmer [Stoeva, Valcheva, 2016]. Also, the market is not static and changes in it create both new opportunities for the development of economic activity and threats to its existence in the long term. Market analysis involves estimating the size and trends of the market, describing the agricultural customers (their location, their needs, their price sensitivity, their market power and market image), identifying the profile of the target segment (age , gender, social status of consumers, how often and where they buy the product, what qualities of the product shape the consumer's purchase decision).

Figure 3. Stages in the process of agricultural management. Source: own

Changes in market conditions require a corresponding change in the strategic and ongoing management of the farm [Nikolov, Anastasova, Radev, Borisov, 2015]. The strategy must have the flexibility to take account of uncertainty and the conditions under which it develops and to allow for changes when necessary. In modern market conditions, where market demand is a critical factor for agricultural business development, it is imperative to conduct regular research and analysis of market requirements.

When making management decisions related to the realization of agricultural production as a starting point for market analysis, it is appropriate to apply Michael Porter's model for determining competition in market segments and their attractiveness and potential for development.

Figure 4. Factors Affecting the Type and Degree of Competition. Source: [Borisov, P., T. Radev, D. Nikolov (2019)].

First of all, the strength of competition of the farms in the market segment, producers of the product, must be analyzed. The presence of a large number of manufacturers makes the competition very strong and the market not particularly attractive due to low profits. Conversely, the monopoly position of the farm gives many advantages. In addition, it is also important how the competition is conducted on the basis of price or on the basis of other product characteristics. For smaller farms, markets are more attractive, where they get advantages not from cost reduction, but from achieving higher quality. Distribution channels aim precisely to deliver these benefits to buyers.

Another important factor, buyers also have influence through their ability to influence the cost of realization, trying to reduce it by raising their quality requirements or pitting farms against each other. This usually occurs when buyers are larger and organized, the market is undifferentiated, and products occupy a large relative share of buyer spending. A good practice in such a case is for farms to unite and lead a common marketing policy and shorten the supply chain.

Products will be available for purchase by end users only if certain activities have been performed to move them. These activities are the essence of distribution and their skillful management is an

important prerequisite for market success. Intermediaries realize the production of the producers and to a certain extent ease their activity. The farmer must analyze the advantages and disadvantages, the benefits and losses of using different intermediaries and consider what distribution strategy to use.

Suppliers are companies that supply (deliver) the necessary goods, raw materials and materials to ensure the production process. A marketing policy aimed at collecting the necessary information, comparison and selection of the offered prices, term of delivery and their quality, terms and methods of payments, additional services, etc. must be conducted with them. Thus, each farm has a selective attitude towards suppliers.

The possibility of new entrants entering the market determines the dynamic nature of the market. In many of the markets of agricultural products (tomatoes, peppers, cucumbers, salads, potatoes), the access of new participants is very easy, which in certain years attracts many producers, thus increasing competition and lowering prices. In other productions (fruit, animal breeding) larger investments and periods are needed for their absorption, which is a kind of investment barrier and prevents a rapid change of the established competition.

The business environment has a significant impact on the development of agricultural activity. This is because each farm operates within the conditions imposed by its business environment.

These conditions are determined by many factors that are external to agricultural holdings. Characteristic of these factors is that they are always dynamic. Therefore, changes in the business environment create conditions for success, but also for uncertainty and threat. Although the future is unpredictable, marketers must be able to determine what is most likely to happen. Entrepreneurs who fail to respond to changes in the business environment leave agriculture unprepared to deal with the changes that occur, which can lead to undesirable results. Therefore, monitoring the business environment factors is vitally important for the survival of the agricultural holding and the achievement of its long-term goals. To keep up with the changes in the marketing environment, marketers will need to perform scanning and analysis.

Scanning the marketing environment is the process of gathering information about the factors of that environment. It includes monitoring secondary sources such as: business, trade, government and other publications and marketing research. It is necessary to determine well what information they need, since not always a lot of information allows accurate conclusions to be drawn.

Analysis of the marketing environment is a process of evaluating and integrating the collected information [Dirimanova, Radev, 2017]. Through it, farmers must be able to determine the upcoming changes, which in turn are the likely threats and opportunities for the functioning of the agricultural holding. All this helps to assess the marketing conditions at the moment and develop a marketing strategy for the future. Marketers offer two general approaches to react to changes in the marketing environment [Nikolov, Boevsky, Borisov, Radev, 2020]. One of them makes it possible to consider the factors of the marketing environment as completely uncontrollable and difficult to predict. In this approach, farms are passive towards the environment. In the second approach, they approach the environment aggressively and attempt to influence the factors determining the marketing environment. It cannot be said which approach is better and successful. The choice of one or the other is influenced and depends on the management philosophy of the farmer, on the goals, financial possibilities, markets, skills, etc.

The task of marketing is to study the market in the most detail and analyze the results obtained for making adequate management decisions by the agricultural producer.

CONCLUSIONS

The management of agricultural holdings in the realization of production must be in accordance with the specifics of the market factors that have a direct connection with the agricultural holding. In this regard, every agricultural holding must study the behavior of consumers in order to attract them. For this purpose, it is appropriate to develop a system of characteristics and indicators by which the market is divided in terms of consumers. Knowing them facilitates the selection of the marketing policy and is especially important when making decisions about the marketing strategy.

Depending on the type of buyers, two types of markets are defined: consumer and industrial. The differentiation of the consumer and industrial market is very important in the realization of the product. The customers of the two markets have different behavior, which requires the application of a different marketing mix, including and distribution solutions. The goal is to find good customers who pay well and on time, appreciating the value of the product offered.

Expanding the market presence is possible using the achievements of the scientific and technical environment. Studying the possibilities of the modern scientific and technical environment is an important prerequisite for the success of agricultural holdings. It is necessary to analyze the technological innovations and changes that have a huge impact on the way of life, on the behavior of consumers and their preferences. Of particular importance are modern means of communication, which can facilitate activities for the sale of agricultural products.

Also for the understanding and knowledge of the market environment, the culture of the participants in the marketing chain occupies an important place. In a sense, culture means the traditions, mores, customs, religion, education, preferences, way of making buying decisions, etc. Each market is characterized by some generally accepted value system that influences the behavior patterns of each individual buyer.

In conclusion to the questions asked, it should be noted that the factors of the marketing environment should be studied, analyzed and evaluated as favorable or not. Moreover, these factors are always dynamic, which is why it is necessary to monitor changes and especially trends in their development.

REFERENCES

- Boevsky, I. (2020). The role of stakeholder management for the development of Bulgarian credit cooperatives. *Bulgarian journal of agricultural economics and management*. Vol.65, No 1
- Borisov, P. & Popova, I. (2021). Approach to change management to achieve a stronger level of competitiveness of wine companies in Bulgaria. *Bulg. J. Agric. Sci.*, 27 (Suppl. 1), 3–9 (Scopus)
- Borisov, P., T. Radev (2020). Profiling the drivers of market power of wineries. The case of Southern Bulgaria. *Journal of Bio-Based Marketing*, vol.2, 2020, 21-29, ISSN 2683-0825
- Borisov, P., T. Radev, D. Nikolov (2019). Young Farmers and New Entrants in Bulgarian Agriculture - Profiling their Challenges and Needs. *Agriculture Economics and Management* 64 (2), 60-71
- Dirimanova, V., T Radev. (2017). The Knowledge Transfer in the Agricultural Sector in South-central Region of Bulgaria. *Bulgarian Journal of Agricultural Science*, Vol. 23 (No 3)

Kolaj, R., P. Borisov, M. Osmani, E. Arabska (2022). Challenges of markets during the post-pandemic in Albania: A philosophical observation on food consumption through the theory of planned behavior. *Journal of Bio-Based Marketing*, vol.2, 2022, 5-12. ISSN 2683-0825

Kolaj, R., P. Borisov, M. Osmani, E. Arabska (2022). Challenges of markets during the post-pandemic in Albania: A philosophical observation on food consumption through the theory of planned behavior. *Journal of Bio-Based Marketing*, vol.2, 2022, 5-12. ISSN 2683-0825

Kolaj, R., P. Borisov, M. Osmani, E. Arabska, T. Radev (2021) Food Markets of conventional Products: A Characterization of Factors Influencing Food Choice. *Journal of Bio-Based Marketing*, vol.2/2021, 5 -10, ISSN 2683-0825

Nikolov, D., I. Boevsky, P. Borisov, T. Radev. (2020) Opportunities for joint marketing of farmers from the region of Smolyan. *Bulgarian journal of agricultural economics and management*. Vol.65, No 1

Nikolov, D., M. Anastasova, T. Radev, P. Borisov.(2015). Status and prospects for the development of small farms. *Avangard Prima*.

Radev, T., P. Borisov, S. Miladinoski. (2019). Intervention Effects of Rural Development Programme on Landscape Management in Bulgaria. *Faculty of Business Economics and Entrepreneurship. International Review* (2019/3-4), 62-72. (Web of science)

Stoeva, T., Valcheva E. (2016). Regional characteristics and trends in the development of agriculture in the South Central region, *Collection of Perspectives for the Development of Education and Science*, Plovdiv.

Yovchevska, Pl. (2015). Vulnerable sectors in Bulgarian agriculture: CAP 2007-2013 impact. *Bulgarian journal of agricultural economics and management*. Vol.60, No 3

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